

Intellectual Property Protection

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When a property is generated using human mind, logic or intellect, it is called as Intellectual Property while when this property is protected in a particular country, and the rights are given to the creator by the Government of a country, then it becomes Intellectual Property Rights. Intellectual Property (IP), when unprotected, cannot be enforced, however, Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) can be enforced only in the country where it is granted. IPR can be divided into different forms based on the scope of protection and the country of protection and not in another. IPR are generally categorized into Patent, Trademark, Copyright and Design. Each of these rights, vary in terms of the scope of protection accorded, criteria for its grant and term of protection. The criteria for grant of any form of IPR are based on the Agreement of Trade Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights and by the national acts of a country. A patent is given for technology that is a product or a process or may be both, for a term of 20 years from the date of filing and should meet the three criteria namely Novelty, Inventive step and Industrial application in order to be granted. Trademark protects both trade and services marks, be it a logo, phrase, a combination of both, smell or a particular tune, for a term of 10 years and its renewable till it is in use. While Copyright is automatically generated once a work is created, however, to enforce the copyright, it has to be registered. The aesthetics of an article is what is protected through Design for a term of 10 years, renewable for another 5 years. It is noteworthy, that the IPR are territorial in nature and would accord rights only in the country where the application is filed and granted. It is also interesting to note that the later three- Trademark, Copyright and Design are also crucial from branding point of view. There are other forms of IP such as Geographical Indications, trade secrets, plant variety, etc. In this article the main focus would be on design protection in India and route to protect in other countries.

Design is the first thing a consumer notices about the product, and sometimes relates to it without knowing or looking at the name. For instance, Toblerone™ Chocolate 's triangle shaped chocolate or the coke bottle without the label would still be identified as Toblerone chocolate and coke. Thereby, this is the value of design in the business world, and thus, the companies desire to protect every improvement in the design. In India, Industrial Designs are governed through the Indian Design Act, 2000 (hereinafter referred to as Act). Section 2(d) of the Design Act 2000 defines "design" as "features of shape, configuration, pattern, ornament or composition of lines or colours applied to any article whether in two dimensional or three dimensional or in both forms, by any industrial process or means, whether manual, mechanical or chemical, separate or combined, which in the finished article appeal to and are judged solely by the eye" (Section 2d of the Designs Act, 2000). The protection is not extended to trademarks as defined under the Trade and Merchandise Marks Act, 1958 or any artistic work as defined in Copyright Act, 1957 or to any mode or principle of construction or a mere mechanical device. In one of the cases Lucky Exports Vs. The Controller of Patents and Designs and ORS, the Calcutta High Court decided that even if a design is functional but if it has some features which are not functional and appeals to the eye, then such a design is registrable (Lucky Exports Vs. The Controller of Patents and Designs and ORS, 2022).

Section 4 of the Act prohibits registration of a design which is not new or original that is not known to the public, or disclosed to public anywhere in India or any other country in tangible form or by use before the date of filing of the application. The section also signifies that the design which is not significantly distinguishable from known or combination of known designs and comprises scandalous or obscene matter cannot be registered (Section 4 of the Designs Act, 2000). A design is considered to be original when it is originating from the author of the design or is an old design but applied in a new way. Another crucial aspect for registration of a design is to ensure that the design is applied to the article and the design is not the article itself. The author him/herself can apply for the design registration on his/her own or jointly with other authors or through an assignee by submitting representation of the design in form of drawings, photographs or graphics. In India, the design registration applications are examined by the Design Office without making any request for examination, abet a different process than followed for patent applications, wherein request for examination is to be filed within 48 months from the date of examination.

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